

Examining survivor function data across multiple trials for kinetics of stroke recurrence

"The Vivli data repository enabled us to access original data from multiple trials, compare estimates, and harmonize data."

- Dr. James Brorson

Researcher(s) or Team: Dr. James Brorson, University of Chicago

Dataset(s) used:

<https://vivli.org/examination-of-survivor-functions-from-socrates-and-thales-trials-for-kinetics-of-stroke-recurrence/>

<https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00009734>

Related publication(s): Brorson, J.R., Giurcanu, M., Prabhakaran, S. and Johnston, S.C., 2023. Vulnerable and Stabilized States After Cerebral Ischemic Events: Implications of Kinetic Modeling in the SOCRATES, POINT, and THALES Trials. *Neurology*.
Doi: 10.1212/WNL.0000000000207904

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Graphic from publication of research showing predicted treatment effects based upon kinetic parameters established by the team's research. In: Brorson, J.R., Giurcanu, M., Prabhakaran, S. and Johnston, S.C., 2023. *Vulnerable and Stabilized States After Cerebral Ischemic Events: Implications of Kinetic Modeling in the SOCRATES, POINT, and THALES Trials*. *Neurology*. Doi: 10.1212/WNL.0000000000207904.

Background:

Stroke is a common and often devastating condition in which blockage of blood flow to a part of the brain leads to its destruction, with corresponding loss of function, producing a variety of symptoms. A person who suffers a first stroke classified as mild is at increased risk of a second, often more severe stroke.

Dr. James Brorson and a team of colleagues set out to examine data gathered from participants in several large trials in the aftermath of a first stroke event, to determine whether treatment decisions could be made more precisely based upon analysis of timing and rates of stroke recurrence.

Process:

Dr. Brorson and his team sought to harmonize, merge, and assess data from three large trials. They accessed data from more than 25,000 participants in order to provide sufficient statistical power to detect modifiers of early and late kinetics of stroke recurrence.

To carry out their analysis, the team developed a two-state kinetic model of stroke recurrence. This model proposes an initial vulnerable state with a higher rate of stroke recurrence which rapidly transitions to a stabilized state with a lower rate of recurrence. They further theorized that this model would fit the survival data for each of these recent trials of acute secondary prevention better than would a model assuming only a single clinical state after the initial minor stroke.

Graphic from publication of research in the journal *Neurology* showing comparisons of estimates in control and active treatment groups across the 3 trials assessed.

Findings:

The research team determined that, across multiple trials of acute secondary prevention after minor stroke or TIA, recurrence of stroke is well-described by a two-state kinetic model postulating vulnerable and stabilized states, with similar kinetic parameters across trials. Their findings also indicated that enhanced antiplatelet regimens only affected the recurrence rates during a brief period in the vulnerable state. This analysis suggests that two distinct states follow acute cerebral ischemic events, and that these states are subject to differential impact of immediate or delayed therapies. These findings have been published in the academic journals *Neurology* and *Stroke*.

The authors are also working on a [second phase of this project](#) to harmonize and curate the data from the first phase into a single large dataset. When complete, they plan to re-share this dataset on the Vivli data repository to support further research in this area, providing additional opportunities for analysis and identification of new methods to prevent stroke recurrence.

Figure 1 Kinetic Models of Stroke Recurrence

Diagram from publication of research in the journal *Neurology* illustrating the different kinetic models of stroke recurrence that underpin the team's research.